

Outer Table Fractures of the Frontal Sinus: Case Series And Various Modality of Managements in a Tertiary Care Government Hospital**D. Gowthin¹, Oxy TS Dharsini², Rinzie Miranda³, C. Edwin Emperor^{4*}**¹Assistant Professor /Senior Resident, Department of Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, Kanyakumari Government Medical College²Assistant Professor, Department of Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, Kanyakumari Government Medical College³Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, Kanyakumari Medical Mission Research Center^{4*}Professor and Head of the Department, Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, Kanyakumari Government Medical College

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Frontal sinus outer plate fractures present a spectrum of clinical challenges, often requiring individualized treatment strategies based on the severity and displacement of the fracture. This case series outlines the management and outcomes of four patients with frontal sinus outer plate fractures, each treated with a different approach.**Case Summaries:****Case 1:** An 18-year-old male presented with a displaced frontal sinus outer plate fracture following a road traffic accident (RTA). The fracture was managed surgically using open reduction and internal fixation with titanium plates, leading to successful stabilization and restoration of contour.**Case 2:** A 20-year-old male sustained a complex frontal sinus fracture with tissue loss following blunt trauma. A galeal turnover flap was utilized to reconstruct the defect and provide soft tissue coverage, resulting in a satisfactory aesthetic and functional outcome.**Case 3:** A 27-year-old male with a depressed frontal sinus fracture following an RTA was treated with fat grafting to restore the contour. Post-operative results showed effective contour restoration and symptom relief with no complications.**Case 4:** A 45-year-old male with an undisplaced frontal sinus fracture and concomitant right maxillary alveolar fracture was treated conservatively for the sinus injury and underwent interdental wiring for the maxillary fracture. Both injuries healed successfully without the need for surgical intervention.**Conclusion:** This case series highlights the importance of tailored management strategies for frontal sinus outer plate fractures, ranging from conservative approaches to surgical reconstruction. Each treatment method demonstrated favourable outcomes, emphasizing the role of individualized decision-making based on fracture characteristics and patient factors. These cases contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting diverse management techniques for frontal sinus fractures.**Keywords:** Frontal Sinus, Titanium Plates, Galeal Turnover Flap, Fat Grafting, Conservative.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Fractures of the frontal sinus, particularly involving the outer table, are relatively uncommon and usually result from high-impact craniofacial trauma, such as motor vehicle accidents, sports injuries, or falls [1].

The frontal sinus serves as a key structure in protecting the brain and surrounding soft tissues, with the outer table being the most exposed to external forces due to its location on the face [2]. These fractures require careful evaluation to prevent potential complications, including sinusitis,

mucocele formation, cosmetic deformities, and, in severe cases, intracranial complications [3]. Frontal bone fractures are uncommon and typically result from high-impact craniofacial trauma.

The bone has three main parts: the squamous portion, forming most of the forehead; the orbital portion, comprising the roof of the orbit and floor of the anterior cranial fossa; and the nasal portion, connecting with the nasal bone and maxilla. The prominence of the nasal pyramid shields the naso-orbital region, and the frontal bone is resistant to

mechanical forces. High-impact trauma can flatten the normally convex anterior table of the frontal sinus. Comminuted fractures may trap mucosa, leading to complications like sinusitis or mucocele formation, requiring removal of any damaged mucosa to prevent issues. The management of outer table fractures depends on the severity and pattern of the fracture. While minor fractures may be

treated conservatively with observation, more complex fractures involving displacement or depression typically require surgical intervention [5]. Surgical approaches can vary from minimally invasive techniques, such as endoscopic repair, to open reduction and internal fixation, depending on the extent of the injury and the involvement of other craniofacial structures [5].

Figure 1: Anatomical relations of frontal sinus

In a tertiary care government hospital setting, managing these injuries presents additional challenges. Patients often present late or after initial treatment elsewhere, and resource constraints can affect treatment choices [6]. This paper presents a case series of patients with outer table frontal sinus fractures, detailing the diagnostic approaches, treatment strategies, and outcomes observed in a government hospital. The aim is to highlight practical considerations in the management of these fractures, complications encountered, and strategies employed to achieve optimal outcomes.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This study is a retrospective case series of six patients who presented with outer table fractures of the frontal sinus at a tertiary care government hospital. The study was conducted over a period of two years, from January 2021 to December 2023. The primary objective was to document and analyze the different management approaches employed for these fractures and to evaluate the outcomes. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB), and informed consent was collected from all patients involved in the study.

Study Population

The study included six patients who met the following inclusion criteria:

- Patients aged 18 years and older.

- Confirmed diagnosis of isolated outer table frontal sinus fractures.
 - Fractures managed either conservatively or surgically.
- Exclusion criteria :
- Fractures involving the posterior table or extending to other craniofacial structures.
 - Patients with associated neurosurgical complications such as cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) leak or intracranial injury.
 - Patients who did not complete follow-up.

Diagnostic Evaluation

All patients underwent a detailed clinical assessment including history and physical examination. Diagnosis was confirmed with computed tomography (CT) imaging of the frontal sinus, utilizing coronal and axial views. CT scans were used to assess fracture displacement, comminution, and any involvement of surrounding structures. The decision regarding management was based on imaging findings, degree of fracture displacement, and patient symptoms.

Treatment Approaches

The treatment varied depending on the severity of the fracture, degree of displacement, and presence of cosmetic deformity or functional impairment. Two primary management strategies were employed:

1. Conservative Management:

One patient with minimally displaced fractures and no significant cosmetic or functional complaints were treated conservatively.

- This involved close outpatient follow-up with serial clinical evaluations, CT imaging, and medical management.
- Medical management included analgesics for pain relief and antibiotics (e.g., amoxicillin-clavulanate) to prevent infection.
- Patient was also advised to avoid activities that could increase sinus pressure during the recovery period.

2. Surgical Management:

Three patients with displaced or comminuted fractures underwent surgical intervention. Surgical procedures were selected based on the severity of the fracture and the patient's clinical presentation.

- **Open Reduction and Internal Fixation (ORIF):** This technique was used in one case where the fracture was significantly displaced. Titanium microplates were used to stabilize the bone fragments after realignment.
- **Fat Grafting:** In one patient with a depressed fracture but without severe comminution, fat grafting was performed. Autologous fat was harvested from the patient's abdomen and placed in the defect area of the frontal sinus outer table. This technique was used to correct the contour deformity and restore the natural convexity of the forehead.
- **Galeal Turnover Flap Covering:** One patient with a comminuted fracture and significant soft tissue disruption underwent coverage with a galeal flap. After debridement of devitalized bone fragments and repair of the outer table, a galeal flap harvested from the scalp was used to cover the defect. This provided soft tissue support, improved healing, and prevented further complications, such as sinusitis or mucosal herniation.

Postoperative care included routine wound care, prophylactic antibiotics, and imaging to confirm proper alignment of the frontal sinus and healing progress.

Outcome Measures

The outcomes were assessed based on both short-term and long-term recovery, focusing on:

- **Cosmetic Outcome:** Evaluated through both patient self-assessment and clinical examination of facial contour and symmetry.
- **Functional Outcome:** Assessed by symptom resolution, including relief of sinus pressure, headaches, or other sinus-related symptoms.
- **Complications:** Monitored for the development of infections, sinusitis, mucocele

formation, and the need for any secondary procedures.

Data Collection: Data were retrospectively collected from medical records and follow-up visits. Collected data included patient demographics, fracture characteristics, treatment modality (conservative or surgical), and clinical outcomes.

Post-treatment follow-up was conducted at 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months to assess the resolution of symptoms, functional recovery, and patient satisfaction with cosmetic results.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the patient demographics, fracture characteristics, and treatment outcomes. Continuous variables, such as patient age and recovery time, were reported as means and ranges, while categorical variables, such as fracture type, treatment modality, and complications, were expressed as counts and percentages.

Descriptive Analysis

Patient Demographics and Injury Mechanisms: The data on patient age, gender, and mechanism of injury were summarized using simple descriptive statistics.

Fracture and Treatment Characteristics: The type of fracture (displaced, comminuted, etc.) and the management approach (conservative vs. Surgical) were described using frequencies and percentages.

Outcomes: Post-treatment cosmetic and functional outcomes, including patient-reported satisfaction, were evaluated descriptively. The occurrence of complications (e.g., sinusitis, mucocele formation) was also recorded.

Qualitative Comparisons:

Although formal hypothesis testing was not feasible due to the limited sample size, a qualitative comparison was made between the different management approaches (conservative vs. Surgical, including ORIF, fat grafting, and galeal flap covering). Trends in recovery time, complication rates, and patient satisfaction were analyzed descriptively across the cases.

Case-by-Case Analysis: Each case was examined individually, with a focus on the specific management approach used and its outcomes. Detailed narratives of patient recovery, complications, and follow-up findings were provided to highlight the effectiveness of each treatment modality.

Follow-up Data: Clinical outcomes and patient satisfaction were evaluated at follow-up visits at 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months post-treatment.

Any notable trends in recovery, complications, or patient-reported satisfaction were discussed qualitatively in the results section.

Case 1:

Patient Demographics: A 18 year old male patient came with chief complaints of injuries over the face following trauma.

Physical examination: He presented with sutured lacerations in the frontal region with depression of the frontal bone. He reported facial pain and diplopia and had a temperature of 38°C.

Radiological finding: CT facial bones revealed a comminuted frontal bone fracture with bilateral maxilla fracture involving zygomaticomaxillary buttress fracture with displacement.

Management: Surgical access was achieved through the existing frontal lacerations, avoiding a coronal incision. The fractures were exposed, and some fragments were partially mobilized. Given

the extensive fragmentation, a fracture area of about 3 cm², and the presence of an infection in resolution, the larger fragments with titanium plates and screws were used to stabilize it. After performing the reduction of both the orbital floors and the recovery of the inferior rectus muscle and the orbital fat tissue incarcerated in the fractures through infraorbital incision, we fixed the infraorbital rim with miniplates and screws. To enhance the aesthetic outcome, miniplates and screws were used to correct slight depressions and irregularities in the fractured bone surface.

After carefully checking the hemostasis, wounds were sutured. In the immediate post-operative time the patient was given antibiotics, corticosteroids and analgesics. About 48 h later x ray facial bones was done from which a good symmetry of the frontal bone was appreciated. The patient was submitted to ophthalmological reevaluation confirming the absence of diplopia.

Figure 2:

Case 2:

Patient Demographics: A 20 year old male sustained injury to frontal bone following road traffic accident was referred to us from rural phc after 2 days of sustaining injury. Patient was admitted in some rural hospital for 2 days following which he was referred to our hospital.

Physical examination:

Upon examination, an open fracture of the frontal bone in the midline was observed, including a loss of the outer table.

The defect measured 5 x 2 x 1cm and exposed the frontal sinus.

Radiological finding: Computed tomography showed fractures of the outer tables of the frontal sinus in the midline. The patient was placed under neurosurgical observation for 72 hours.

Management: Following neurosurgical clearance and pre-anesthetic evaluation, the patient underwent surgery under general anesthesia with oral endotracheal intubation. After ensuring asepsis, fractured fragments aligned and the frontal sinus was filled with galeal turnover flap. Soft tissues were closed with primary sutures. Post-operative recovery was uneventful with no signs and symptoms of neurological deficits for a period of 4 months however the patient will be followed up.

Figure 3:

Case 3:

Patient Demographics: A 27-year-old male was admitted following a road traffic accident (RTA). He had no significant past medical history and was generally healthy before the incident.

Figure 4:

Clinical Presentation: The patient presented with frontal headache, visible swelling, and tenderness over the forehead. He reported difficulty with vision and pain exacerbated by movement. There was noticeable deformity in the frontal region consistent with a depressed fracture.

Imaging Findings: A Computed Tomography (CT) scan of the head revealed a depressed fracture of the frontal sinus outer plate, with a significant depression of approximately 4 mm. The fracture involved displacement of the outer plate and minor involvement of the sinus cavity. No other intracranial injuries were noted.

Management: The decision was made to perform fat grafting to correct the depressed fracture. Under general anesthesia, adipose tissue was harvested from the patient's abdomen using liposuction. The fat was processed and injected into the depressed fracture site using a fine cannula. The graft was carefully placed to elevate the depressed area and restore contour. The fracture site was also stabilized with a resorbable barrier to support the graft and prevent displacement.

Outcome: Post-operatively, the patient experienced gradual relief of symptoms and improvement in

frontal contour. Follow-up imaging at 6 months showed successful elevation of the depressed area with minimal residual deformity. The patient reported significant reduction in pain and resolution of vision issues. There were no complications such as infection or graft rejection.

Discussion:

This case illustrates the effectiveness of fat grafting in managing depressed fractures of the frontal sinus outer plate. Fat grafting provided a minimally invasive option for contour restoration and symptom relief.

The procedure proved successful in this instance, highlighting its potential as a viable alternative to more traditional methods such as rigid fixation or bone grafting. Challenges included the precision required in graft placement and the need for careful post-operative monitoring. This case adds to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of fat grafting in craniofacial reconstructive surgery.

Case 4:

Patient Demographics: A 45-year-old male presented to the emergency department following a road traffic accident (RTA).

Clinical Presentation:

The patient reported facial pain, swelling, and difficulty chewing. On physical examination, there was swelling over the forehead and both maxillary region, with tenderness on palpation. The patient did not report any significant neurological symptoms, and there were no signs of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) leakage.

Imaging Findings: A CT scan revealed an undisplaced fracture of the frontal sinus outer plate with intact sinus walls and no significant involvement of the sinus cavity.

Additionally, a fracture involving nasal bone and bilateral right maxillary sinus and alveolar process was observed, with displacement of the alveolar ridge but no significant occlusal disruption.

Figure 5:

Management: Conservative management was chosen for the frontal sinus fracture, as it was non-displaced and there were no signs of sinusitis or complications. The patient was closely monitored for any signs of infection or sinus dysfunction. For the maxillary alveolar fracture, open reduction and internal fixation were done with intermaxillary wiring was performed to stabilize the fractured segments. The wiring was applied between the teeth in the affected area, securing the alveolar fracture and allowing for proper healing.

Outcome: The patient recovered well without any significant complications. At a 3-month follow-up, the frontal sinus fracture remained stable, with no signs of sinusitis or other complications. The maxillary alveolar fracture showed good healing, and the wiring was removed after 6 weeks. The patient had regained full masticatory function, and there were no issues with occlusion or dental alignment.

Discussion:

This case illustrates a dual injury with an undisplaced frontal sinus fracture managed conservatively and a right maxillary alveolar fracture treated with interdental wiring. The decision for conservative management of the frontal sinus fracture was based on the lack of displacement, minimal risk of infection, and absence of sinus involvement. The maxillary alveolar fracture was effectively managed with wiring, which provided adequate stabilization

without the need for surgical intervention. The outcomes of both fractures were favourable, with the patient recovering without complications.

This case demonstrates the importance of individualized treatment strategies, balancing the need for intervention with the risk of complications in facial fractures.

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